

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) shelx

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: shelx

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0106 A	Wavelength=1.54184
Cell:	a=13.7608(5) b=7.3316(3) c=13.3194(7)	alpha=90 beta=111.655(5) gamma=90
Temperature:	150 K	
	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1248.94(10)	1248.94(10)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C16 H30 N6 O2, 2(C1 O4), 2(H2 O)	?
Sum formula	C16 H34 Cl2 N6 O12	C16 H34 Cl2 N6 O12
Mr	573.39	573.39
Dx,g cm-3	1.525	1.525
Z	2	2
Mu (mm-1)	2.983	2.983
F000	604.0	604.0
F000'	607.50	
h,k,lmax	16,8,15	16,8,15
Nref	2202	2125
Tmin,Tmax	0.513,0.551	0.463,1.000
Tmin'	0.452	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.463 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.965 Theta(max)= 66.577

R(reflections)= 0.0801(1300) wR2(reflections)= 0.3190(2125)

S = 1.143 Npar= 175

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT340_ALERT_3_B Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds 0.0106 Ang.

Author Response: this value could be due to the little bit high first element of the principal mean square atomic displacements U

Alert level C

PLAT029_ALERT_3_C _diffn_measured_fraction_theta_full value Low . 0.965 Why?
PLAT084_ALERT_3_C High wR2 Value (i.e. > 0.25) 0.32 Report
PLAT223_ALERT_4_C Solv./Anion Resd 3 H Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range 10.0 Ratio
PLAT245_ALERT_2_C U(iso) Hw1 Smaller than U(eq) O2 by 0.034 Ang**2
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C Large U3/U1 Ratio for Average U(i,j) Tensor 2.2 Note
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A) O2 - Hw2 . 1.02 Ang.
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance 4.807 Check
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance 2.090 Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.595 76 Report
PLAT975_ALERT_2_C Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.75A From O4 0.41 eA-3
PLAT976_ALERT_2_C Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.71A From O2 -0.60 eA-3
PLAT976_ALERT_2_C Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.97A From O4 -0.59 eA-3
PLAT976_ALERT_2_C Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.88A From O2 -0.45 eA-3

Alert level G

PLAT072_ALERT_2_G SHELXL First Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large 0.20 Report
PLAT244_ALERT_4_G Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C1 Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1 109.6 Degree
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 2 Note
PLAT909_ALERT_3_G Percentage of I>2sig(I) Data at Theta(Max) Still 34% Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 1 Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 1 Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
1 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
13 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
7 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
9 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
9 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
3 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
0 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 03/05/2019; check.def file version of 29/04/2019

